

256, 300 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3840 (—OH), 1730 cm^{-1} (α -pyrone). It furnished a tetra-O-methyl ether indistinguishable from tetra-O-methyl ether of ellagic acid².

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Chemical Constituents from the Stem Heartwood of *Guazuma tomentosa*, Kunth (DC) and Stem of *Clerodendron indicum* (Linn) Kuntze

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PETROLEUM ether extract of stem heartwood of *Guazuma tomentosa* afforded friedelin, tetracosanoic acid, β -sitosterol and 3-O-acetyloleanolic acid while from the stems of *Clerodendron indicum* (24S)-ethylcholesta-5, 22, 25-triene-3 β -ol and β -sitosterol were isolated.

Guazuma tomentosa (Sterculiaceae) is a moderate sized tree, cultivated in gardens and is said to be of considerable medicinal value¹. A perusal of literature revealed that some work has been reported on its stem bark², leaves^{3,4} and flowers⁵.

Clerodendron indicum (Verbenaceae) is a large shrub, cultivated for ornamental purposes and is said to be of considerable medicinal value⁶. Leaves of this plant have already been studied by different workers^{7,8}.

The present note deals with the examination of stem heartwood and stems of *G. tomentosa* and *C. indicum* respectively.

Guazuma tomentosa: Completely dried and coarsely powdered stem heartwood (15 kg) of *G. tomentosa* was exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract (10 g) was chromatographed over silica gel and eluted with petrol-benzene mixtures of different proportions when the following compounds were obtained. The identification of the compounds was made through m.p., mixed m.p., Co-tlc studies and preparation of some derivatives.

Friedelin: $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M^+ , 426), m.p. 258-260° (petrol) (Lit.⁹ m.p. 260-262°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2950, 2890, 1725, 1470, 1380, 1360, 1230, 1190, 1120 cm^{-1} ; oxime, m.p. 290-292°; epifriedelinol, m.p. 276-277° by reduction with NaBH_4 .

Tetracosanoic acid: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$ (M^+ , 368), m.p. 87° (Me_2CO) (Lit.¹⁰ m.p. 87.5-88°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2900, 1705, 1480, 1300, 940, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} ; methyl ester, m.p. 58-59°.

β -Sitosterol: White needles m.p. 136-137° ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$) (Lit.⁹ m.p. 136-137°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 2900, 2830, 1640, 1470, 1370, 1065 and 810 cm^{-1} ; acetate, m.p. 125-126°; benzoate m.p. 142-143°.

3-O-Acetyloleanolic acid: $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ , 498), m.p. 255° (petrol) (Lit.¹¹ m.p. 258-260°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300-3060, 1730, 1690, 1460, 1390, 1325, 1030, 970, 900, 800 cm^{-1} ; methyl ester, m.p. 221°; oleanolic acid, m.p. 305° by alkali hydrolysis.

Clerodendron indicum: Air dried and coarsely powdered stems (5 kg) of *C. indicum* were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) and the concentrated extract (6 g) was chromatographed over silica gel when the following compounds were obtained. The compounds were identified by direct comparison (m.m.p., Co-tlc, ir) with authentic samples.

(24S)-**Ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3-ol**: $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ (M^+ , 410), m.p. 148° (petrol) (Lit.⁹ m.p. 151-153°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3450, 3230, 2950, 1640, 1190, 1135, 1060, 1030, 960, 885 and 800 cm^{-1} ; acetate m.p. 140°.

β -Sitosterol: Colourless flakes, m.p. 136-137° ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$); acetate m.p. 124-125°; benzoate m.p. 143-144°.

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